

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF CRIME PREVENTION AMONG MINORS AND YOUTH BY PREVENTION INSPECTORS

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Abstract: The article discusses the subjective causes and conditions of juvenile delinquency, factors related to the personality of minors, objective causes and conditions for the commission of offenses, the rights and obligations of prevention inspectors in working with them, as well as a scientific and practical analysis of their activities.

Keywords: offense, juvenile, socio-moral, prevention, rehabilitation, legal awareness, legal culture, crime, subjective causes.

Today, for our youth to become well-rounded individuals, our fundamental law, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, stipulates in Article 41: "Everyone has the right to education. Free general education is guaranteed by the state. School affairs are under state control," which guarantees the rights of minors in the field of education. The educational process plays an important role in developing a minor's intellectual potential, worldview, and knowledge, as well as in shaping them into individuals who contribute to society.

Most articles of the Constitution are related to the rights and interests of minors, including the special emphasis placed on it in the preamble of our constitution. The phrase "conscious of their high responsibility to present and future generations" indicates that the constitution was adopted not only from today's perspective but also with awareness of the high responsibility to future generations, that is, to minors and youth.

Along with protecting the rights and freedoms of minors, identifying and taking measures to eliminate the causes and conditions that negatively affect them, organizing the prevention of neglect and delinquency among them, and taking measures for the social adaptation and rehabilitation of minors who have committed offenses and are in need of social protection are important tasks in this area.

Identifying and eliminating the causes of juvenile delinquency and the conditions that contributed to it, as well as forming law-abiding behavior in minors, is one of the urgent problems of today. Because the study and analysis of the causes of crime and the conditions contributing to them is one of the main elements of the subject of criminology, which in itself also serves to increase the effectiveness of crime prevention.

There are various approaches to the causes of juvenile delinquency and the specific aspects of the conditions that contributed to them, the study of which from a scientific point of view has not only theoretical, but also practical significance.

V.P. Kashepov believes that juvenile delinquency, as well as "general" adult delinquency, in our opinion, is a manifestation of socio-economic and political instability, the emergence of ethnic conflicts, and the violation of social and moral foundations.

In juvenile delinquency, upbringing plays an important role. At the same time, the personal characteristics of minors, their lack of moral upbringing, and the underdevelopment

of legal awareness and legal culture are among the reasons leading to their commission of crimes. Because whoever recklessly violates moral norms will certainly recklessly violate the law. Theft of small amounts of money from home, smoking, drinking, violence against peers or younger ones, initially done for one purpose - for personal pleasure or to solve certain mental problems in this way or to show off to those around them, but later all of this no longer satisfies him, and as a result, he tries to test new sensitive feelings, and at this age their need for money and valuables increases. For example: due to the family's inability to purchase modern technical means: computers, various audio-video equipment, mobile communication devices, many young people try to achieve their goals by stealing others' property, stores or warehouses, or secretly appropriating property belonging to close relatives, parents (in most cases, small amounts from parents' clothes, bags, or other places where they put money).

Determining the causes of the emergence of criminal behavior requires, first of all, the study of the characteristics of the social environment in which it arose, since criminal behavior, if taken in general terms, manifests itself not as a result of subjective behavior inherent in a particular person, but as a result of subjective and objective processes, conditions, and relationships. From this point of view, it is necessary to clarify the issue of the influence of social processes on individual behavior.

The commission of crimes by minors and their susceptibility to various negative influences is the biggest problem in any society, even in developed countries. Because a child who is not yet able to fully control himself, who does not fully understand the essence of his actions, may commit offenses or crimes under the influence of the environment, social reality.

If minors are poorly raised or are influenced by various negative social vices, these shortcomings will also affect their future life. It has been proven that the earlier a person enters the path of criminal activity, the longer it lasts and the more dangerous it becomes[1]. The main factor contributing to the emergence of juvenile delinquency is not urbanization or other demographic processes, but primarily the shortcomings of upbringing in the family, school, work collective, and family life.

It is advisable to study the subjective and objective causes of juvenile delinquency and the conditions contributing to them.

The subjective causes and conditions of juvenile delinquency are phenomena related to the personality of the minor, while the objective causes and conditions can be seen as a negative influence of the social environment, except for those related to the minor himself. In particular, the subjective causes of juvenile delinquency include the worldview and spiritual world of the minor, interests and needs, values and life plans, legal consciousness and level of legal culture, lifestyle, goals and directions, motives. The objective causes of juvenile delinquency include the unhealthy environment in the family, economic and political instability in society, the negative influence of the environment outside the family (school, mahalla, small groups), the crime zone, as well as the mass media (internet, social networks).

The subjective conditions of juvenile delinquency include its demographic and socio-psychological characteristics, in particular, character, temperament, age, gender, education, health (disability), legal capacity, as well as the creation of favorable conditions for the commission of a crime by a minor.

The objective conditions for juvenile delinquency include shortcomings in the state management system, non-compliance with the requirements of laws and regulations,

irresponsibility and negligence of the subjects carrying out and organizing the prevention of juvenile delinquency, as well as the fact that the victim himself creates conditions for the commission of the crime through negative behavior and lifestyle.

Parents' indifference to their children's upbringing and entrusting their children's upbringing to others are also contributing to negative situations. Today, it is observed that some parents leave their children to elderly parents, relatives, acquaintances, and neighbors with great hopes, that is, to provide their children with better material support, to hold their weddings more luxuriously than others, and to have their clothes in abundance, while leaving to work elsewhere to earn money.

The fact that the majority of minors serving sentences for crimes, or more precisely, more than 70%, are divorced or are children of parents who have left their families for a long time to work in another country, confirms our opinion[2].

According to UNICEF's short report on the impact of migration on children in Uzbekistan (2024), parental migration negatively affects children's emotional well-being. About 33% of the surveyed children feel unhappy, while 21% live in constant anxiety. Half of the children reported that their mood immediately deteriorated after their parents left for foreign countries. Consequently, parents are obliged to support and raise their children until they reach adulthood, and if they do not fulfill or do not fulfill this obligation properly, they will be held liable under the relevant article of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility. Moreover, they will be deprived of parental rights, and the state will have to take the child under its protection, appoint a guardian or trustee.

It is known that children should be under the influence of upbringing not only during lessons, but also outside of classes. Therefore, school administrations must constantly inquire about how their students live in their homes and spend their free time, studying and taking responsibility for their upbringing. The fact that a minor is left unattended by parents or the public, or falls under the influence of the educational and upbringing community, awakens and strengthens in them a sense of recklessness, as a result of which conditions arise for the commission of an offense by a minor[3].

Studies have shown that many parents or their substitutes did not know how to properly raise their children, and some did not think about proper upbringing at all, as a result of which their underage children committed crimes[4]. Also, in some families, underage children committed crimes because they showed excessive care and love for children, did not control their behavior, did not pay attention to their friends, external contacts, what they did in their free time, etc. However, practice confirms that excessive care forms arrogance, dependency, disrespect for others, and a negative attitude towards physical labor in adolescents.

Thus, it is necessary to further improve the system of comprehensive influence (family-school-mahalla) in preventing juvenile delinquency and the above-mentioned negative situations. At the same time, we must also explain the norms of Sharia, which are the source of our national values, in instilling the harmful consequences of crime, particularly the consumption of alcoholic beverages, drugs, and psychotropic substances, in the minds of minors. The Prophet (peace be upon him) said, "Every intoxicant is forbidden." (Narrated by Imam Muslim). In another hadith, he warns: "Whoever kills himself with poison will be tormented by the fire of Hell on the Day of Judgment" (Narrated by Imam Tirmidhi) [5].

State bodies and the general public responsible for the prevention of juvenile delinquency must determine the causes and conditions for:

- the presence of a constant conflict situation in the family;
- low level of education or lack of pedagogical knowledge of parents;
- incomplete family (absence of a father or mother);
- material shortages in the family;
- an unhealthy environment in the family (consumption of alcohol, prostitution, etc.)
- neglecting the child's upbringing as a result of parents being too busy with work or household chores;
- long-term departure of parents abroad for work or study;
- low level of legal awareness and legal culture of the minor;
- the impossibility of attending various clubs or sports activities of interest in the minor's free time;
- lack of interest or neglect by parents or guardians of the minor's mental state;
- parents' absence from work;
- negative influence of the preschool teacher on the upbringing of the child;
- not raised in a preschool educational institution;
- lack of control or weak control by the school administration during or outside of school hours;
- indifference of adult neighbors or relatives to the upbringing of the child;
- neglect of the use of the Internet and mobile communication facilities;
- a large number of unorganized youth in the mahalla at the place of residence;
- identifying and developing roadmaps for eliminating such negative phenomena as inadequate organization of free time outside of studies and conducting preventive work will help reduce juvenile delinquency.

Consequently, in identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions of juvenile delinquency: firstly, non-compliance with the established rules of morality in society; secondly, commission of administrative offenses; thirdly, commission of crimes; fourthly, taking into account the shortcomings and achievements of preventive measures implemented in practice, the effective organization and implementation of preventive measures serve, firstly, the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of minors; secondly, the early prevention of juvenile delinquency.

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